

potassium hydroxide solution canary yellow needles were obtained.

The compounds produced vivid colours (orange to brown) when treated with conc. sulphuric acid. The presence of α , β -unsaturated ketonic group was ascertained by absorption bands near 1661 to 1680 cm^{-1} in the infrared absorption spectrum of these compounds. All compounds analysed satisfactorily for C and H elements.

The antimicrobial activity of these compounds was tested by Zone inhibition techniques with *S. aureus* using benzoic acid as standard. All the compounds were found to be less active than standard.

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Chemical Examination of the Inflorescence of *Ocimum kilimandscharicum* Gurke

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OCIMUM kilimandscharicum commonly known as 'bantulsi' belongs to the family *Labiatae*. A sweet smelling bush it grows wild with long decorative inflorescences. In view of its commercial importance in India as a source of camphor, the plant has been extensively studied¹⁻⁴ on various aspects including chemistry. The present work deals with the chemical investigation of the inflorescence which has not been reported so far.

1077 g of air-dried mature inflorescence was steam distilled to remove the volatile fraction. This weighed 3.5 g from which 0.4 g of camphor crystallised out. The inflorescence left after steam distillation was extracted with rectified spirit in a soxhlet apparatus. The alcohol-free extract was repeatedly washed with ether. The ether washings were divided into neutral and acidic fractions.

The neutral fraction contained 32.2 g of a light yellow oil which was saponified with 10% alcoholic caustic soda. The nonsaponifiable portion weighed 1.2 g. This on chromatography gave a crystalline-sterol from the benzene fraction (yield 0.2 g). It crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p.

138°C, $[\alpha]_D - 36$ (chloroform). It gave an acetate, m.p. 124°C and a benzoate, m.p. 144°C. The sample was established as β -sitosterol from comparison of mixed m.p. with an authentic sample.

The acidic fraction, a light brown solid weighing 32.6 g gave a violet colour, with Liebermann-Burchard reagent and was triterpenic in nature. 10 g of this acid was esterified with diazomethane and the crude ester was chromatographed over alumina. Since no satisfactory separation of the constituent esters could be obtained from this chromatography, the different fractions were mixed together and acetylated with pyridine and acetic anhydride on water bath. The acetylated methyl esters, however, separated nicely on chromatography over alumina. Fraction A (yield 2.8 g) appeared in the benzene eluent in a crystalline form. It was crystallised from methyl alcohol in fine needles, m.p. 217-19°C. It gave a violet colour with L.B. reagent and produced yellow colour with tetranitromethane. On alkaline hydrolysis it furnished a methyl ester, m.p. 198°C, $[\alpha]_D + 72$ (chloroform). The compound was identified as methyl oleanolate from mixed m.p. determination with an authentic sample. Fraction B (yield 0.6 g) came in the tail runs of the benzene eluent and crystallised from alcohol as silky needles, m.p. 245-46°C. It also responded to both L.B. reagent and tetranitromethane. On hydrolysis it gave a methyl ester, m.p. 170°C, $[\alpha]_D + 56$ (chloroform). The compound was identified as methyl ursolate from a mixed m.p. determination with an authentic sample.

The inflorescence of *O. kilimandscharicum* was thus found to contain 0.04% camphor, 0.02% β -sitosterol, 0.86% oleanolic acid and 0.18% ursolic acid.

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The Use of *p*-Rosaniline as Diazo Coupling Component for Azoic Dyes

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THOUGH basic dyes are well known for their high tinctorial value as well as brightness, they have been found to be much less resistant to the action of light and soap. The 'naphthols' have been known for good fastness but they lack brightness. We have therefore tried to combine the two by using the basic dye as an amine to be diazotised and coupled with 'naphthols'. In this paper we have reported the diazotisation of *p*-rosaniline and the fastness of shades obtained therefrom.